

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: RODINE****FIRST NAME: BAKAM KAMGUE****PROGRAM CODE: DGEP****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 5%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Essay Writing (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 6-12)
2. Punctuations (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 15-23)
3. American VS. British English (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 33-39)
5. What Is a Style Guide and Why Would I Need One? (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 40-42)
6. CMS Crib Sheet (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 43-56)
7. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 58-62)

THE FUNDAMENTALS OF PAPER WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

An academic essay is one produced from an academic work or academic research. According to (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 4), to write this paper, you must start the essay, research the topic, organize your ideas, write the essay, reference the essay, edit the essay, hand the essay in, and know or understand some rules of thumb for writing a paper. To write a good essay, a student should know how to use punctuation, American versus British English. He may also know the percentage of plagiarism authorized in the documents, what style guide is, and why should he need one. He may also know the CMS Crib Sheet and Latin Abbreviations and Expressions.

After reading the ACA-401D course pack revised by Dr. Kabiru Gulma and Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck, watching the tutorial videos, and how to use response papers, I saw that what I need to learn is like make the difference between American and British English.

This response paper will discuss four primary concepts I have learned from the course pack for period one and the tutorial video. It will be punctuation, American VS. British English, and plagiarism. What is a style guide, and why would I need one?

2) PUNCTUATIONS

Learning punctuation can be easy for some people, but it is also tricky if you want to learn another language or if you want to translate some document. I think that the course on punctuation is essential for the reasons mentioned above, and I also find the section on quotation marks extremely helpful, as it specifies the use of single quotation marks for direct speech or a quote and double quotation marks for direct speech or a quote within that. (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 23).

3) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

The principal fact here is to understand US and UK English and the differences between the two. They are both variants of English and are also similar and different. There are many categories of differences between standard American English (SAE) and standard British English (SBE), like the same concept, different terms or expressions or the same word, and differences in style, connotation, and Frequency (Hire a car – rent a car) (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 28).

4) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 34). When writing a paper, the most important thing to do is to avoid plagiarism. The writer should properly cite the author or mention the source that has provided information he is using to avoid plagiarism and permit the reader to know the source of where the information they are writing about came from and what the harm is. There are many methods to cite an author, such as quotations and paraphrases. I think that it is essential to note that it is not necessary to cite authors all the time. Your work would look like it is not your own recherche.

5) WHAT IS A STYLE GUIDE AND WHY WOULD I NEED ONE?

It is essential to know what a style guide is and why a writer needs a particular style guide. A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent. (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 41). It is important to note that when writing your paper, it is not necessarily to have a personal

style, but that of the school or company according to the fact that you should be coherent and consistent.

EUCLID recommends using the Chicago Rules (Turabian), or American English but the writer can use other internationally recognized Rules. I think that it is essential to hand on a type of style if you want to use it, in order to ensure consistency in your written output.

6) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

Latin abbreviations and expressions are most used by technical communicators. In the coursepack ACA-401D, I have learned many abbreviations and expressions that I have never seen or heard. For example, I always thought that eadem was written idem. It is important to know it all because you can read a document with Latin abbreviations or expressions that you don't know.

7) CONCLUSION

It was a very great experience to read ACA-401D period one course pack and also to watch the videos made by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck. I think I would continue to watch it till the end of the program in DGEP.

I realized when learning that I need to read many things and improve my English and to become a good student why not a writer? I usually say that, you don't learn what you know, but learn what you don't know. I found that what I don't know is a lot, so I have many things to learn.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, Director. 2024. *Basic ACA-401/ACA-401D Tutorial*. Vimeo video.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.